

Comparative evaluation of CO₂ capture by *N,N*-dimethylamine *N*-ethylamine chitosan and *N*-cinnamoyl chitosan

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Abstract : Coal burning for power generation aggravates emission of greenhouse gases like carbon dioxide (CO₂) and other. In the present work, authors explored the process of capturing of CO₂ from the flue gases by means of chemical absorption. *N,N*-Dimethylamine *N*-ethylamine chitosan salt and *N*-cinnamoyl chitosan were synthesized for the capturing of CO₂ from the flue gas. Aqueous *N,N*-dimethylamine *N*-ethylamine chitosan salt and *N*-cinnamoyl chitosan 10 wt% in 1 litre demineralized water has been selected for removing CO₂ from the combustion gases. The concentration of CO₂ in the flue gases ranges from 9 to 14% after combustion and 100% removal of CO₂ for 10 min and 2 min at flow rate 1 liter per min. This is having the removal capacity about 1.9 g and 0.4 g of CO₂ per liter of 10% *N,N*-dimethylamine *N*-ethylamine chitosan salt and *N*-cinnamoyl chitosan respectively.

Keywords : *N*-Cinnamoyl chitosan, CO₂ capture, flue gas, *N,N*-dimethylamine *N*-ethylamine chitosan salt.

Introduction

Carbon dioxide encompasses about 0.03% of the earth's atmospheric volume, but due to the burning of fossil fuels and deforestation, this fraction has augmented approximately 25% since ancient era¹. Burning of coal results in release of CO₂, the major anthropogenic source of greenhouse gas². Coal fired thermal power plants, once built; operate for a very long time about 30 years. This implies that coal plants, once constructed, will steadily emit CO₂ over a long period. This entail that the existing problem of CO₂ emissions from coal power plants is very likely to be compounded in the future. These emissions can be reduced by a variety of measures, such as (i) improving combustion efficiency of the power plant, (ii) fuel substitution to lower or zero-carbon fuels, (iii) CO₂ capture technologies and (iv) increasing the use of renewable energy sources. If no actions will be taken, the global manmade CO₂ emissions will significantly increase and support the ever known green gas effect. In principal among the types of fossil fuel used, coal has the highest carbon content, resulting in coal-fired power plants having the highest output rate of CO₂ per kilowatt-hour produced³.

Attenuation of the emissions of CO₂ from coal-fired

power plants is the target of the present work. To accomplish the same, it describing the process of capturing of CO₂ by synthesized *N,N*-dimethylamine *N*-ethylamine chitosan salt and *N*-cinnamoyl chitosan and comparison of feasibility have been discussed.

Experimental

Materials :

Chitosan (98.1% deacetylated), methyl iodide, sodium borohydride, acetaldehyde, *N*-methylpyrrolidone (NMP), ethylamine, methylamine, acetone, cinnamic acid, diethyl ether, methanol and sodium iodide.

Methods :

Synthesis of N,N-dimethylamine N-ethylamine chitosan :

In the 1% w/v acetic acid (original pH 3.7 ± 0.5) was dissolved 500 mg of chitosan. The required amount of acetaldehyde was added to above chitosan solution and stirred for 1.5 h. Ethylamine amine solution was added for acquiring the pH 4.5. Finally, 2.0 mL of 10% sodium borohydride solution was added for 5 min and allowed to stirred the reaction mixture for 2 h. The ethylamine chitosan was precipitate out which was washed with distilled water and then Soxhlet extracted with ethyl alcohol

and ether (1 : 1 v/v) for 3 days to give ethylamine chitosan in high yield.

Methylamine (2.0 mL), methyl iodide (5.0 mL) and sodium iodide (600 mg) was added to the dispersed solution of ethylamine chitosan (200 mg) in 10 ml of *N*-methylpyrrolidone. The dispersed reaction mixture was stirred at 60 °C for 5 h. Finally, the reaction mixture was quench with acetone to precipitate *N,N*-dimethylamine *N*-ethylamine chitosan⁴.

Chemical reaction :

Chemical reaction :

Table 1. CO₂ Removal time

Time (min)	% CO ₂ Removal	
	<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylamine <i>N</i> -ethylamine chitosan salt	<i>N</i> -Cinnamoyl chitosan
0	11.47	11.47
1	0.00	0.00
2	0.00	6.89
3	0.00	9.50
4	0.00	10.89
5	0.00	11.23
6	2.59	11.56
7	6.98	11.49
8	9.87	11.52
9	11.09	11.48
10	11.62	11.57

Fig. 1. Comparison removal of CO₂.

Results and discussion

The % CO₂ is removed from the flue gas by means of a chemical solvent is summarized in Table 1 and graphical presentation in Fig. 1. The concentration of CO₂ in the flue gases ranges from 9 to 14% after combustion and 100% removal of CO₂ for 10 min and 2 min at flow rate 1 liter per minute. This is having the removal capacity about 1.9 g and 0.4 g of CO₂ per liter of 10% *N,N*-dimethylamine *N*-ethylamine chitosan salt and *N*-cinnamoyl chitosan respectively.

Conclusion

Synthesized *N,N*-dimethylamine *N*-ethylamine chitosan salt is better performing in live flue gas than *N*-cinnamoyl chitosan. Hence, it is beneficial to optimise and use synthesized *N,N*-dimethylamine *N*-ethylamine chitosan salt further for pilot scale studies.

References

1. S. P. Raghuvanshi, A. Chandra and A. K. Raghav, *Energy Conversion and Management*, 2006, **47**, 427.
2. K. Sudhakar, S. Suresh and M. Premalatha, *Int. J. Chem. Res.*, 2011, **3**, 110.
3. Ioana Ionel, Padurean Ioan, Cebucean Dumitru, Popescu Francisc, Viorica Cebucean (Harea), Gavrilă Trif-Tordai, Dungan and Luisa Izabel, *Metalurgia International*, 2009, **14**, 40.
4. S. A. Aswar and P. R. Bhagat, *Int. J. Knowledge Engineering*, 2012, **3**, 135.
5. M. Diab, A. El-Sonbati, M. Al-Halawany and D. Bader, *Open Journal of Polymer Chemistry*, 2012, **2**, 14.